

HEAT TREATMENT RESPONSES OF PARTICULATE TiC REINFORCED TOOL STEEL COMPOSITES

S. H. Kim¹ and D. W. Suh²

¹Graduate Institute of Ferrous Technology, POSTECH
77 Cheongam-Ro, Nam-Gu, Pohang, Gyeongbuk, South Korea
Email: kzzang0911@postech.ac.kr, web page: <http://cml.postech.ac.kr>

²Graduate Institute of Ferrous Technology, POSTECH
77 Cheongam-Ro, Nam-Gu, Pohang, Gyeongbuk, South Korea
Email: dongwool@postech.ac.kr, web page: <http://cml.postech.ac.kr>

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ABSTRACT

To achieve high hardness and good resistance against erosive wear and corrosion, a great attention has been paid to ceramic reinforced steel matrix composites. However, studies on the influence of heat treatment in steel matrix composites have been rarely reported, in spite of its huge impacts on the mechanical properties of iron based alloys. In this study, heat treatment responses of a particulate TiC reinforced tool steel matrix composite, which is fabricated by pressure infiltration casting, have been investigated.

1 INTRODUCTION

A particulate TiC reinforced tool steel matrix composite was fabricated using pressure infiltration casting by Korea Institute of Materials Science. Pressure infiltration casting, a form of liquid infiltration, makes molten metal infiltrated into a preform of ceramic reinforcement by applying a high pressure with inert gas[1]. Advantages of this process includes inexpensive fabrication of composites and production of net-shape components.

SKD11 was used as a tool steel matrix of the composite. Chemical composition of SKD11 is shown in Table 1.

C	Cr	Mo	V	Ni	Si	Mn	P	S
1.40- 1.60	11.0- 13.0	0.80- 1.20	0.20- 0.50		<0.40	<0.60	<0.03	<0.03

Table 1 : Chemical composition of SKD11 (wt.%)

Figure 1 shows a micrograph of the composite before heat treatment, taken by an optical microscope. TiC particles, whose volume fraction is approximately 60%, are uniformly distributed within the steel matrix, although the composite has some defects because the process of pressure infiltration casting is still being developed.

Figure 1 : Optical microscopic images of TiC/SKD11 composite

The composite was then heat-treated in the temperature range of 920 to 1070°C for two hours in order for the steel matrix to be austenitized, followed by air-quenching for hardening. This is for the purpose of observing heat treatment responses of the composite during the hardening process and seeking the optimized condition of that process.

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION(1)

2.1 XRD results

Before dealing with heat treatment responses in other heat treatment conditions, we have investigated the TiC/SKD11 composite and an unreinforced SKD11 austenitized at 1010°C, the temperature at which SKD11 is usually heat-treated. XRD results are shown in Figure 2, which says that both TiC/SKD11 and SKD11 contains retained austenite after being hardened.

Figure 2 : XRD results of TiC/SKD11 composite and the unreinforced one after being austenitized at 1010°C and air-quenched

Retained austenite fraction, measured by comparing integrated intensities of bcc Fe peaks and fcc Fe peaks with a compensation, is 19% for SKD11 and 28% for TiC/SKD11 composite. This is opposite to the results from [2].

2.2 Lattice parameter and Carbon content

With the information of where austenite XRD peaks occur, austenite lattice parameters are obtained by using Bragg's law and a relationship between the interplanar spacing d of (200) in fcc Fe and the lattice parameter a :

$$2d \sin \theta = \lambda \quad (1)$$

$$d = a/2 \quad (2)$$

where θ is an angle between the incident beam and a (200) plane and λ is 1.5406Å for x-ray produced by a copper target.

The result of obtaining austenite lattice parameters for TiC/SKD11 composite and SKD11 is shown in Figure 3. The difference between the two lattice parameters is 0.005Å on average.

To assess what the 0.005Å increase in austenite lattice parameter means in terms of carbon content, a series of first-principle calculations is devised. The calculations are based on the framework of density functional theory (DFT) [3, 4] and carried out by using Vienna ab initio simulation package (VASP) [5, 6] with project augmented-wave (PAW) potentials [7, 8] and with the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) proposed by Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerhof (PBE) for the exchange-correlation terms [9].

Figure 3 : Austenite lattice parameters for SKD11 and TiC/SKD11, obtained by XRD peak positions

Two supercell structures are used for the calculations. One is Fe₃₂C₁, which corresponds 0.67 wt.% of carbon content. The other is Fe₁₂₈C₃ containing 0.50 wt.% C, which is similar to the carbon content in the austenite phase of SKD11: 0.51 wt.%. In both structure, every carbon is located in an octahedral site and non-magnetic calculations are conducted.

The calculated results are displayed in Table 2. Applying thermal expansion to the calculated results gives values in the parentheses. The errors between the calculated lattice parameters and the measured ones are due to a limit of the first-principles calculation in expressing paramagnetic systems, so only the difference of 0.007Å in the calculated lattice parameters is to be considered. The result indicates that 0.17 wt.% increase in carbon content is supposed to expand the austenite lattice by 0.007Å. By interpolation, 0.005Å corresponds to 0.12 wt.% carbon increase in austenite.

Carbon content in γ	Structure	Lattice parameter
0.50 wt.%	Fe ₁₂₈ C ₃	3.462 Å (3.505 Å)
0.67 wt.%	Fe ₃₂ C ₁	3.469 Å (3.512 Å)

Table 2 : Austenite lattice parameter obtained by first-principles calculations

2.3 Retained austenite fraction and Carbon content

A combination of martensite start temperature (M_s) equation [10] and Koistinen and Marburger's equation [11] can provide predictions on how much more austenite is retained after hardening as adding 0.12 wt.% carbon into a prior austenite phase:

$$M_s (\text{ }^\circ\text{C}) = 539 - 423[\%C] - 30.4[\%Mn] - 17.7[\%Ni] - 12.1[\%Cr] - 7.5[\%Mo] \quad (3)$$

$$V_\gamma = \exp[\beta(M_s - T_q)] \quad (4)$$

where every [%element] means its weight percent in austenite, V_γ is a retained austenite fraction, T_q is the temperature of a quenching medium, and β is a factor associated with transformation rate, depending on steel grades.

The chemical composition of austenite in SKD11 at 1010°C is obtained by a method based on thermodynamics, using Thermo-calc [12]. This information gives M_s temperature, which leads to $\beta = -0.0077$ as substituting 19% for V_γ and 20°C for T_q . Using this β value enables the retained austenite fraction to be calculated, with the austenite chemical composition being changed. Finally, 0.12 wt.% increase in carbon content of austenite in SKD11 is supposed to produce 25 vol.% of retained austenite, which is close to the experimentally measured value, 28%.

This indicates that an increase in carbon content due to TiC dissolution has a significant effect on the heat treatment response of TiC reinforced steel matrix composites in terms of retained austenite fraction. Since reducing the amount of retained austenite is an important issue in tool materials, our results propose that carbon increase in steel matrix of composites should be

considered in designing the heat treatment paths.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION(2)

3.1 Retained austenite fraction with different austenitizing temperatures

Using XRD in measuring the retained austenite fraction of steel matrix composites produce quite large deviation because peak intensities of steel matrix are too low. MSAT, made by Metis Instrument, is therefore used to measure retained austenite fractions for the rest of this study. It directly gives a volume fraction of bcc Fe by measuring the magnetic moment at saturation, so the deviation is smaller than 0.5 vol.%.

Figure 4 shows changes in retained austenite fraction by different austenitizing temperatures. The trend is that the higher austenitizing temperature, the more austenite is retained. These results can be analyzed by referring to phase diagrams for SKD11 in Figure 5, which is drawn by thermodynamics calculation using Thermo-calc. SKD11 phase diagram says that the austenitization of SKD11 is done in the two-phase region with M7C3 carbides. Austenitizing at a higher temperature makes more M7C3 carbide dissolve into austenite, which leads to an increase in carbon content of austenite. As calculated by Thermo-calc, changing the austenitizing temperature from 920°C to 1070°C monotonically increases the austenite carbon content from 0.30 wt.% to 0.65 wt.%. Since carbon is one of the most effective austenite stabilizing alloying elements, high temperature austenitization consequently produces much retained austenite.

Figure 4 : Retained austenite fraction of TiC/SKD11 composite according to different austenitizing temperatures

Figure 5 : Phase diagrams for SKD11

The finding that an increase in carbon content of steel matrix is a dominant factor of leaving more retained austenite enables the amount of the carbon increase to be calculated. This can be done by

combining Equation (3) and (4) and regarding other terms except the carbon concentration as fitting parameters of regression analysis, finally leading to this:

$$\ln(V_\gamma) = 2.3414 * [\text{wt.\%C}] - 2.5031 \quad (5)$$

Figure 6 is the result of calculating the overall carbon content in TiC/SKD11 matrix by using Equation (5). The steel matrix in TiC/SKD11 composite is supposed to contain 2.0 wt.% carbon, which is 0.5 wt.% higher than in an unreinforced SKD11.

Figure 6 : Temperature - Retained austenite fraction curve with different overall carbon contents

3.2 Hardness change with different austenitizing temperatures

Figure 7 shows the result of hardness measurement as changing the austenitizing temperature. The hardness of an unreinforced SKD11 increases as raising its austenitizing temperature until 980°C, above which the hardness almost stops increasing. To analyze this result, we refer to previous studies on a relationship between martensite hardness and its carbon content[13], as seen in Figure 8. From calculations using Thermo-calc in the temperature range of 920°C to 1070°C, the carbon content in austenite of SKD11 varies from 0.30 wt.% to 0.65 wt.%, which is displayed as the red dashed lines in Figure 8. Within that range, the slope of martensite hardness change decreases as its carbon content increases. In addition, raising the carbon content brings about reduction in the amount of martensite due to austenite stabilization. To sum up, the combining effect of the slowdown of the increase in martensite hardness and the reduction in martensite volume fraction is supposed to make SKD11's hardness saturated in the high temperature region.

Figure 7 : Vickers hardness of TiC/SKD11 composite according to different austenitizing temperatures

Figure 8 : Summary of martensite hardness data from literatures by G. Krauss[13]

In Figure 7, the hardness of TiC/SKD11 composite remains almost unchanged as being austenitized at different temperatures. In the previous analysis of retained austenite fraction in the composite, we found that the steel matrix of TiC/SKD11 composite would contain 2.0 wt.% carbon, which is 0.5 wt.% higher than SKD11. Calculations using Thermo-calc says that austenite in TiC/SKD11 matrix would have carbon concentration in the range of 0.50 wt.% to 0.80 wt.%, which is displayed in Figure 8 by the blue dashed lines. Within this region, martensite hardness is not likely to increase much as adding more carbon into it. This phenomenon is supposed to be the reason why the hardness of TiC/SKD11 composite changes little with different austenitizing temperatures.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Heat treatment responses of a particulate TiC reinforced SKD11 tool steel matrix composite have been investigated. XRD results say that the steel matrix of TiC/SKD11 composite has more retained austenite than an unreinforced SKD11 after quenching from austenitization at 1010°C. By analysing a relationship between austenite lattice parameter and carbon content using a series of first-principles calculations and combining a martensite start temperature equation and Koistinen-Marburger equation, an increase in carbon content due to TiC dissolution is found to be the cause of getting more retained austenite. Our interpretation of the trend in hardness change of TiC/SKD11 composite also requires the idea of an increase in carbon content in composite matrix. In this sense, changes in chemical composition of the steel matrix in TiC reinforced steel composites are significant in determining the overall properties, which indicates the necessity of taking this phenomenon into account in designing a heat treatment cycle of TiC/Steel composite.

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